

3 Poems by Maroof Shah

Range bael dolum - Ahad Zargar

My Love, freshness of the youthful flower is gone
That is my pain
Unguarded is the treasure trove of secrets
That is my heart's pain
Wounded by thousands wounds
I sawed my body to pieces
Then my body became a flute
That is my heart's pain
Aflame is my body
And more fanning of the flame
Burnt to ashes
That is my heart 's pain
My sandalwood has turned blue
Dyed in saffron
Tongue tied is the bulbul
That is my heart's pain
Purposely I glanced at the wheel of samsara
It is as It has been
[Six¹ and ten² were driving me](#)
Having taken the nectar, the bee has gone into a retreat
Processing the nectar
The spider has tightened its noose on the self
That is my heart's pain
What I bought by selling my life
I kept cheaply for sale
The ignorant are still hesitant to buy
That is my heart's pain
Ahad Zargar is watchful of the heart
Feigning a poet
He is summoning houris of the Garden of Paradise

The Poet Calls: Hymn to the Morning and Praise of the Last Age..... Krishan Joo Razdan

Morning has dawned, open your eyes
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
The sun of the Self shines its light
Outside and inside is the Sky of Consciousness.
Open your eyes, don't close the windows
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Your black hair is fading and graying
Why don't you heed the message?
Time has gone, and returns with changed colours
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Time is like performance of a troupe.
Get unburdened, swim along

(Fill its kitty with all and sundry)
That is why it has thrown up a newer play
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Reckon that knowledge is illumination
With mind's eyes, contemplate Shiva
Let not the wind of thoughts arise
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Don't be late in turning towards mindfulness
Put on the clothes of gnosis
Become mindful, overcome laziness
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
From the mountains darkness is retreating
The universe is lighting up
See your face in the Mirror of Nonduality
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Muster your strength and perfect the path with the Master
The Lord will guide you on the Straight Path
You will receive in the measure you can conceive
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
A moment of attention fetches a night of union
Dawn is their guide
From it is born the blessed time that lifts spirits
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Waking up is an achievement
What does it cost?
Hopeless people have been greeted by light
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
With the footwear of action, the Dharma is trodden
Go to the pilgrimage of the Self on the boat of your body and mind
Dive in *bhakti* and enjoy the sweetness of love
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
The last age is the best of ages
God is pleased with eating and drinking
The last hour has great blessings
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Speed on through the three stages of life
Seek the freedom of forest dweller, sacrifice the life of household
Rest is only the Name of the Lord
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Hail the Lord of Time
This is the Guide
Experiencing and enjoying, see the Countenance
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Welcome the reign of Time
Wear the crown of Mindfulness
Charge the bow and strike
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
As all the four approached the Lord
Privileged place granted to the forest dweller
Acknowledge and praise the Lordly Station

Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Receive the grace of the stages
In the heat of the fire burn the dross of inattention
Only in this age one finds bloom
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Sleep appears tempting this time
The Lord grants guidance this time
Don't forget the Lord this time
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
What mighty beings visit you!
Which souls can afford sleep this time?
The boat to the straight path is on the bank
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Blooming are the flowers of devotion
Hail the wakeful people
Minding one's business this time
Banish sleep, banish sleep.
Birds will sing
Krishan will be the golden oriole
With love sing songs of Krishna
Banish sleep, banish sleep.

Khudayi Fojdar

God! There are few lovers of you left now
There are many self righteous fellows
An army of theologians
Having reserved all the seats in heaven for themselves
They are busy in dispatching your servants to hell
Because they love you so much
They can't tolerate your enemies
And they find your enemies everywhere
As if Satan is in control of all the affairs
As if the whole world is infidel
And all are astray
Except themselves
And they alone are worthy of you.
They presume to be your personal secretaries
Dividing men in your name
Coveting the riches of the other world
Seeking houris and not you
They have no kind words for the lovers
For those madmen called mystics
The Gnostics who know you alone
Distracted neither by this world nor that world
They see you alone
But your policemen
Are ever persecuting them
Are policemen also needed in your kingdom, my God?

God! There are lawyers and prosecuting officers
Fighting cases for you
When did you appoint them?
They have not seen you
Who could see you and not dance in ecstasy?
They have not tasted you
As they continue to covet worldly things
God! Show them a glimpse of your face
So that they cease fighting for you and instead love you
And leave your lovers in peace

Bionote:

Muhammad Maroof Shah holds Master's degrees in Philosophy, English, and Veterinary Parasitology, and has undertaken doctoral research on *The Problem of Nihilism and Absurdist Impasse in (Post)Modern Literature: A Metaphysical Appraisal of Samuel Beckett and Albert Camus*. He has written columns for leading English dailies, contributed numerous book chapters and research papers, and co-edited journals such as *Kashmir Veterinary Journal* and *Animal Science Quarterly*. He has also co-compiled and edited manuals on sheep farming and co-translated the first volume of the medieval Qur'anic commentary *Tafsir-e-Rehmani* by Makhdoom Alauddin Ali Mahaimi. His books include *The Problem of Evil in Muslim Philosophy: A Case Study of Iqbal*, *Muslim Modernism and the Problem of Modern Science*, *Perennial Philosophy in the Postmodern World*, *Revisiting Sufism*, and *Revisiting the God Debate*. His interests focus on the interface of religion, philosophy, and mysticism, particularly within the Islamic tradition in dialogue with other traditions. He blogs at maroofshah.blogspot.com and contributes to *The Times of India* blog *Sophia*.